

Seasonal Influences on Zooplankton Diversity of a Sacred Grove Freshwater

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Abstract

A study in the Banapureeshwar temple pond (BTP) at Kumbakonam, Thanjavur district, Tamil Nadu, India, was conducted from March 2018 to February 2019 to assess the seasonal variations in the population density of zooplankton, which serve as an ecological indicator of aquatic ecosystems. The study identified a total of 35 zooplankton species, with copepods comprising 13 species, Cladocera comprising 8 species, rotifers comprising 11 species, and ostracoda comprising 3 species. The Shannon-Weiner diversity index (H') ranged from 1.13 to 2.606, while Margalef's species richness index ranged from 0.7797 to 3.1, indicating a moderately rich zooplankton diversity in the BTP lentic ecosystem. Among the identified zooplankton groups, copepoda were found to be the dominant group, accounting for 45.7% of the total, followed by rotifers (25.7%), cladocera (23.2%), and ostracoda (5.5%). The mean seasonal abundance of zooplankton followed the order of monsoon > pre-monsoon > post-monsoon > summer.

Keywords: Zooplankton, Diversity indices, Pond ecosystem, Cladocera, seasonal influence

Introduction

Till the 1980s, fish production in India was largely achieved by inland fisheries, which include both capture and culture fisheries. However, due to an increase in the number of water control structures and the degradation of natural water resources, capture fisheries have declined [1]. Factors such as diminishing natural resources and the high cost involved in capture fishing have led to the search for a potential and cost-effective alternative to capture fisheries. Aquaculture emerged as a cost-effective alternative to capture fisheries during the last two decades and developed into a second major industry next to agriculture [2]. Globally, India ranks second, succeeding China in aquaculture. Aquaculture contributes about 44% of the global fish production [3] and provides approximately 50% of the fish consumed worldwide [4]. The fish production from inland fisheries in India was 65% during 2017–2018, out of which 50% was contributed by culture fisheries.

Aquaculture faces significant challenges such as poor growth, low nutrient content, and high mortality rates in cultured fish. To address these issues, artificial diets are often used to feed larval fish, but they may not fully meet the nutritional needs of the fish due to their underdeveloped digestive systems lacking necessary enzymes [5]. Therefore, supplementing their diet with live feed enriched with essential nutrients is crucial for successful larval fish rearing in aquaculture. Zooplankton, known for its high nutritional value, is a particularly beneficial live feed for developing fish larvae [6]. The abundance and species composition of zooplankton in aquatic environments are influenced by various physical, chemical, and biological factors [7]. Factors such as water size and quality play a significant role in the existence of zooplankton, as they are sensitive to parameters like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, total alkalinity, and free CO₂. Consequently, changes in the physicochemical composition of aquatic ecosystems can impact the relative composition and abundance of zooplankton, making them valuable indicators for monitoring aquatic ecosystems [8]. By surveilling zooplankton diversity, fecundity, size, structure, and community dynamics, we can assess the extent of pollution in aquatic ecosystems [9]. This information underscores the importance of maintaining a healthy aquatic environment for the successful development and sustainability of aquaculture.

Ponds are crucial components of freshwater ecosystems on a global scale and are significant in the conservation of biodiversity [10, 11, 12]. They serve as important biodiversity hotspots, hosting a high number of local, rare, and endemic species that are often not found in other aquatic ecosystems. Pollution in this ecosystem has resulted in the accumulation of large amounts of discarded waste, which has harmed aquatic life. In this context, our study is focused on studying the species diversity of zooplanktons in the Banapureshwar temple pond to determine the effect of seasonal variations, changes in physical and chemical factors of the pond ecosystem on the zooplankton species diversity and richness.

Materials and methods

Study area

The Banapureeshwar temple pond is located at 10°57'N latitude and 79°23' longitude, was sampled in the present study (Fig.1). It was recently renovated in 2015 as part of an effort by the government to manage the freshwater ecosystem. The water level is constantly maintained by the municipality by filling it with water from external sources.

Sampling of zooplankton and water quality parameters

The sampling sites BTP-North, BTP-South, BTP-East, and BTP-West were selected for monthly collection of zooplankton and water quality analysis between March 2018 and February 2019. The results were interpreted seasonally as summer (March to May), pre-monsoon (June to August), monsoon (September to November), and post-monsoon (December to February) using the methodology outlined in [13]. Water quality parameters such as temperature, pH, conductivity (EC), turbidity, salinity, dissolved oxygen (DO), and total dissolved solids (TDS) were determined in the laboratory following the standard protocol of 14. Plankton samples were collected from the subsurface layer of Banapureeshwar temple pond in the early morning (6 a.m. to 7 a.m.) using Henson's standard plankton net (150 m mesh) in a zigzag fashion horizontally at a depth of 50 to 100 cm 15, and preserved in 5% formalin. Zooplankton numbers were quantitatively estimated using Sedgwick Rafter counting cells.

Identification of zooplanktons

The planktonic biomass collected was segregated based on zooplankton groups under a binocular zoom dissection microscope with the help of a fine needle and brush. Individual species were stained with Eosin 13 and observed using a trinocular microscope (Model BXL) attached to a USB camera (MIDCE-5C). Standard manuals, textbooks and monographs were referenced for the identification of different species of zooplankton [16, 17, 18, 19] using a compound microscope.

Biodiversity indices and statistical analysis

The seasonal variations of physicochemical variables of water were determined using a one way ANOVA and Post Hoc Turkey Test. The intra and inter-relationships between physicochemical parameters and zooplankton biodiversity indices were subjected to Pearson's correlation analysis using IBM-SPSS (v.25.0). The species diversity, richness, evenness and dominance indices were calculated using [20] Shanon-Weiner's (1949) index, [21] Margalef's (1958) richness index, [22] Pielou's (1966) evenness index and Dominance index with Paleontological Statistical software (PAST).

Result and Discussion

Seasonal variations in the physical and chemical parameters of freshwater ecosystem

The hydrology of a freshwater pond ecosystem significantly influences the species composition and distribution pattern of planktonic organisms [23]. Environmental factors such as temperature and physicochemical parameters including pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), salinity, conductivity, turbidity, and total dissolved solids (TDS) play a crucial role in the development of phytoplankton, which in turn is essential for the existence of zooplankton. Table 1 presents the variations in the physicochemical parameters of water during different seasons at BTP. The influence of seasonal variations on the physicochemical properties of BTP has shown a significant effect on the species composition, diversity, richness, evenness, and dominance of the zooplankton community. The water temperature in summer was $30.03 \pm 1.91^\circ\text{C}$, while the post-monsoon season exhibited a minimum temperature of $28.11 \pm 2.02^\circ\text{C}$. The increase in temperature during the summer season as observed in this study might be due to the increased length of the day and the concomitant increase in solar radiation [24, 25, 26]. Water temperatures between 13.5 and 32°C are ideal for the growth of zooplankton [27, 28]. Temperature is the most important factor that influences the pH, salinity, conductivity, and solubility of gases in water. Further, they also trigger the dominance of small zooplankton [29, 30, 31, 32].

High pH was observed during the monsoon and post monsoon (7.740 ± 0.14 and 7.74 ± 0.28 respectively), whereas minimum pH (7.15 ± 0.01) was observed during the months of summer. Temperature, anthropogenic activities, and the increased rate of photosynthesis by phytoplanktons all influence the pH of water. [33] Kurbatova (2005) stated that pH above 8.5 is considered highly productive with respect to zooplankton. The pH of BTP was found to be in the range of 7.15 to 7.74, with lower pH levels observed during the summer season and a gradual increase in pH as the monsoon progressed. The rise in pH of the freshwater ecosystem was attributed to the decomposition of plants and organic materials [34], as well as the low temperature during the monsoon period [35]. [36] Sharma et al., (2013) reported high pH during monsoon seasons (winter) in Birpur temple pond, which was in agreement with the present findings.

The dissolved oxygen (DO) in freshwater is influenced by various environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, air pressure, and photosynthetic activity. Low temperatures generally increase the solubility of oxygen. In this study, a high level of DO (3.28 ± 0.03 mg/l) was found during the post-monsoon season, while a low level of DO (3.22 ± 0.08 mg/l) was observed during the summer. The lower DO during summer may be attributed to the decomposition of organic matter and the respiration of planktonic organisms. High levels of DO in aquatic ecosystems are indicative of good water quality and high productivity. Aquatic organisms are highly sensitive to salinity, and an increase in water salinity can reduce the population density and diversity of zooplankton [37]. The salinity of BTP was found to be

highest during the summer (0.80 ± 0.03 ppt) and lowest during the monsoon months (0.65 ± 0.12 ppt). The elevated salinity levels during the summer and post-monsoon periods were influenced by the rise in water temperature, with water evaporation at higher temperatures being a contributing factor [31].

TDS and EC in aquatic ecosystems increase due to anthropogenic activities and the inflow of pollutants, leading to contaminated water [38, 39, 40, 41]. BTP recorded high TDS (1.03 NTU) and low TDS (0.88 NTU) during the monsoon and summer, respectively. The mean TDS value of BTP was much higher than the standards proposed by WHO, indicating that the BTP was polluted because of anthropogenic activities such as worship practices by devotees. The inflow of freshwater during the monsoon might be responsible for low EC at BTP. High turbidity in BTP during the monsoon months might have resulted because of the inflow of slit-laden water [42, 34]. The one-way ANOVA (post hoc turkey test) revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in all of the water variables tested across seasons.

Diversity and distribution of zooplanktons

The zooplanktons are ecological indicators that aid in monitoring pollution, chemical, physical and biological conditions of the freshwater ecosystem. Several previous studies documented the presence and distribution pattern of zooplankton groups such as copepods, cladocera, rotifera, and ostracods in freshwater pond ecosystems [43, 44, 45].

The identification of zooplankton species at BTP revealed a total of 35 species belonging to 4 different groups, namely Copepoda, Cladocera, Rotifera, and Ostracoda. Copepoda dominated the zooplankton species (13 species) followed by rotifers (11 species), Cladocera (8 species) and ostracoda (3 species) (Table 2). The percentage of different classes of zooplanktons observed in BTP was copepods (45.7%), cladocera (16.6%), rotifers (25.7%) and ostracoda (12%) (Fig.2A). The mean seasonal abundance of zooplanktons were in the order of monsoon > premonsoon > postmonsoon > summer (Fig.2B).

In BTP, 13 species copepods dominated the zooplankton species (Fig.3), which indicates the abundance of diatoms and blue-green algae. These phytoplanktons form the basic and important food source for copepods [46]. Among the copepods, *Sinadiaptomus indus* was found to be the dominant species in BTP. The most commonly found copepods in South India were *Sinadiaptomus indus* [47]. Cladocera recorded 8 species (Fig.3). The population of cladocera was high during monsoon season. *Daphnia magna*, *Moina micrura*, *Ceriodaphnia corunuta*, *Leydigia leydigia* and *Diaphnasoma sarsi* reported low population density among cladocera during summer. BTP showed the presence of 8 species of *Branchionus* out of the 12 identified species of Rotifera (Fig.3), with the maximum population observed during the monsoon season. A study by [48] Tidame and Shinde, (2012) indicated the dominance of *Branchionus* species in the temple pond at Nasik. Ostracoda was the least dominant group found in BTP (Fig.3). *Cypris protuberata*, *Euencypris bispinosa* and *Cyprinotus nudus* were the only species recorded in BTP. *Cypris protuberata* dominated the ostracoda population during summer and premonsoon. The maximum zooplankton population in summer and the lowest population in winter in BTP were consistent with the findings of [49] Yadav and Singh

(2018) at Chapakaiya Pond and [44] Krishna and Kumar (2017) in the Kollore region of Andhra Pradesh. The dominance of copepods followed by rotifers in temple ponds located in West Bengal was earlier documented by [50]. Further, the presence of *Mesocyclops* and *Thermacyclops* copepods indicates the eutrophication of water bodies [31].

Cladocerans were one of the major groups of zooplanktons in BTP. The dominance of *Diaphanosoma*, *Daphnia*, *Ceriodaphnia*, *Moina* species of cladocera indicate a high nutrient load of BTP since they are found to occur in high numbers under conditions of eutrophication [51, 52, 53, 54]. Similarly, *B.calyciflorus* (Rotifer), is considered a good indicator of eutrophication 52 55 was found throughout the year in BTP.

The relationship between the population density of zooplanktons and physic-chemical parameters of BTP was analysed using Karl Pearson's correlation matrix (Table.3) Temperature showed positive correlation with the population of rotifers ($r=0.197$) and ostracoda ($r=0.489$). pH was negatively correlated with ostracoda ($r=-0.080$). Similarly, DO was negatively associated with cladocera ($r=-0.594$). Rotifers ($r=0.280$) and cladocera ($r=0.146$) showed positive association with conductivity. Turbidity was positively associated with all the identified classes of zooplanktons. [30] Manickam et al., (2018) reported that pH and temperature were highly instrumental for the diversity of zooplankton in Ukkadam lake, Coimbatore. The positive correlation of water temperature with population density of ostracods ($r = 0.340$) was in agreement with the findings of [55] Rajagopal et al., (2010) in the perennial ponds of Virudhunagar district, Tamilnadu, India.

The PCA biplot (Fig.4) clearly indicated that temperature was correlated with the population density of rotifers. The other physicochemical variables such as pH, salinity, conductivity, DO, TDS and turbidity were highly influential on the population density of cladocera and ostracoda during the monsoon, and turbidity was positively correlated with copepoda during the premonsoon. A similar positive correlation of temperature, pH, turbidity and TDS with zooplankton diversity and abundance was reported earlier [30, 55, 33].

The measures of biodiversity indices serve as crucial indicators of ecological status [56]. [45] Devi et al. (2013) reported the biodiversity indices of zooplankton species in the Birpur temple pond, with the [20] Shannon-Weiner diversity index ranging from 0.39 to 2.98, [21] Margalef's species richness index between 2.92 and 2.96, an evenness index in the range of 0.89 to 0.91, and a dominance index of 0.86 to 0.88. In the present study, the Shannon diversity index ranged from 1.095 to 2.606, evenness was in the range of 0.8371 to 1.032, and the richness index was 0.7797 to 3.1 among the different seasons (Table 4). The current zooplankton data show low diversity combined with high evenness and low richness, possibly due to a lower number of species diversity and dominance of a single species. This is consistent with previous literature, as [30] Manickam et al. (2018) reported a Shannon diversity index in the range of 1.551 to 2.133 and evenness of almost 0.969 in Ukkadam Lake, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. The richness index was between 0.7 and 1.217. Similarly, in a study conducted in three different ponds in Kumbakonam town, the richness index was in the range of 0.961 to 0.982, indicating moderate species richness [57]. Therefore, the zooplankton in ponds located in Kumbakonam city showed a similar pattern of diversity

indices. [34] Gogoi et al. (2019) stated that a [20] Shannon diversity index and [21] Margalef's species richness index above 2.9 indicated moderately rich diversity, and [22] Pielou's evenness index of > 0.98 indicated an even distribution. Based on this interpretation, the diversity indices obtained from the present study suggest that BTP has moderate species diversity and is meso-eutrophic in nature.

Conclusion

The study clearly indicated that temperature, pH, TDS and turbidity played a major role in the zooplankton abundance and diversity in BTP. Further, the influence of pH was crucial for the high population density of zooplankton during monsoon and the pre-monsoon season. The decrease in zooplankton numbers during the summer season could be attributed to the prevailed high temperature. The study suggests continuous monitoring of pond ecosystems to predict the impact of climatic variations on the diversity and distribution pattern of the freshwater zooplankton community for the identification of sentinel and sensitive species in the process of formulating an effective conservation strategy.

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